

Original Research Paper

The Effecting Factors of Personality Trait and Shopping Attribute on Purchase Intention: A Case Study of PinDuoDuo-Commerce in China

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ABSTRACT

Purpose –The purpose of the study was to discuss the effects of emotional trust, personality traits, functional value, and cognitive involvement on purchase intention. **Design/Approach/Methodology** - This study used three frameworks from previous studies to create a new conceptual framework. This study explores the factors that influence purchase intention through a data analysis approach. **Findings** – This study provides the factors that influence purchase intention. Our study is about the relationship between emotional trust, personality traits, cognitive involvement and functional value and consumer purchase intention. **Research Limitations/Implications** –There are several limitations in investigating the factors that affect consumers' purchase intention to influence purchase intention. Due to the paucity of previous studies on this topic and the fact that previous studies were used for specific purposes. This, combined with the current epidemic of the new coronavirus, led to limitations in the data we collected.

Originality/value - This study will examine and derive the important influencing variables that affect purchase intention.

Keywords - emotional trust, personality traits, cognitive involvement, functional value, consumer and purchase intention.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

This paper explores purchase intent. Younger generations prefer online shopping to conventional offline buying. Online shopping saves them time, avoids traffic delays, and provides them more flexibility to do what they want. They can phone ahead to reserve things, pay for the order, and wait for home delivery. Some things can be delivered within 24 hours thanks to technology and logistics. Most firms face opportunities and problems from technological improvements and an increasing number of products. Many companies perform in-depth investigations on consumer buying intentions. These studies can help organizations prioritize the manufacture of modern items and save money by better matching consumer buying intent. Purchase intent is a consumer's inclination to buy. Consumer attitudes toward a product or brand along with external circumstances create a consumer's purchase intention and are a good predictor of consumer behavior, which is a subjective predisposition to buy a product. Understanding consumer purchasing intentions is crucial

to many organizations' growth, which can improve sales and other income. Many corporations fight in price wars because they believe low prices influence consumer purchase decisions, which is undesirable. The factors that influence consumers' purchase intention are not just price, but also personality traits (Kao, 2017), functional value (Ramayah et al., 2016) in shopping qualities, cognitive engagement (Zhu et al., 2019), and emotional trust (Dunning et al., 2012). Companies must examine purchasing intentions to grow in a competitive market. Consumer research spans centuries. Personality differences are one of the key elements determining a consumer's decision to buy. An individual who doesn't like sports will be less enthusiastic about buying sports goods than an art student. External emotional elements also affect individual personality characteristics, which affect consumers' purchase intention. A non-sporty person may buy sports goods for relatives and friends who love sports. Functional value influences consumers' purchase intentions. Seasonal changes alter the functional value of goods, causing a reduction in sales of goods that sold well in the prior quarter. To prevent

unnecessary losses, organizations must make acceptable judgments about the functional worth of their products (The functional value is written a little less and it would be better to expand it more). COVID-19 caused numerous malls and eateries to close last year, prompting consumers to shop online. Many businesses have moved online. Major corporations have modified their business operations to accommodate online buying. Companies can assist consumers to make good judgments by researching their buying intentions. It can help reduce costs and wasteful spending. Rent, utilities, and decor for a retail opening. It reduces stress, allowing the organization to spend more time on an effective and profitable conversion process. The complex and diversified consumer wants to boost the likelihood that they'll choose the same product from the same company again. Consumers create emotional trust during buying. When they need a product, they'll choose one they've already utilized. If a corporation can understand and improve emotional trust, it will raise the likelihood of people buying its items. Otherwise, they'll lose customers.

A customer's buying intent determines a business's future. As more people shop online, companies are studying performance-related factors. A company's production and sales can be more flexible and effective if it understands consumer buy intent. This study aims to identify what influences consumers' buying intentions. First, the study's findings will help companies better focus their programs. Rapidly focusing on purchasing intent will enhance corporate earnings. Businesses can utilize this study to create growth-appropriate work plans that reduce employee labor and enhance productivity. Spending project money where they're required most multiplies their effect. This study will also benefit management, leaders, supervisors, and staff. By removing unnecessary effects, employees can focus on key ones. Reducing unneeded travel, business collaboration, etc., and focusing on aspects like personality qualities, cognitive engagement, and emotional trust cuts corporate expenses, minimizes employee stress, and enhances company vitality and drive. This study helps customers, too. By discovering and evaluating buy intents, it's possible to manufacture things that better meet consumer expectations, cut purchasing time, and expedite shopping. Businesses can satisfy varied consumer groups by understanding personality attributes and adopting targeted product changes. Emotional trust and cognitive engagement can turn shoppers into loyal users. This will save consumers

time and energy, reduce the risk of failure when trying new things, and protect their interests.

1.2 Research Objectives and Research Questions

As mentioned earlier, there are several factors that influence consumers' purchase intention. In terms of the independent variables, affective trust, cognitive involvement, and functional value have an effect on the dependent variable purchase intention, while the independent variable personality traits have an effect on both affective trust and purchase intention. Therefore, this study precisely examines the relationship between these variables that influence purchase intention.

1. To explain the effect of affective trust on purchase intention.
2. To explain the effect of personality traits on affective trust.
3. To explain the effect of personality traits on purchase intention.
4. To explain the effect of cognitive involvement on purchase intention.
5. To explain the effect of functional value on purchase intention.

These aims align with the following research questions:

1. Does the customer's emotional trust have a substantial effect on his or her purchase intention?
2. Do customers' personality traits have a significant effect on their emotional trust?
3. Do the personality traits of customers have a significant effect on their purchase intention?
4. Does cognitive involvement have a significant effect on customers' purchase intention?
5. Do Functional value have a significant effect on customers' purchase intention?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theories of Each Variable

2.1.1 Emotional trust

Emotional trust is a prerequisite for a person to make certain decisions, in contrast, some studies have identified and explored a number of mechanisms of online trust, including trusted third parties (Palmer et al., 2000; Van & Lieshout, 2001) and online reputation systems (Kollock, 1999; Resnick et al., 2000). Tan and Thoen (2000) the trust model was created and includes two fundamental elements: faith in others things and trust in trust control protection mechanisms. Also, other studies have proposed ways that can promote trust in e-commerce, such as secure third-party proxy technologies (Cassell & Bickmore, 2000; Papadopoulou et al., 2001). Some studies have also new theoretical models of trust in e-commerce are proposed. Friedman et al. (2000) a

more thorough trust typology has been put forth by McKnight and Chervany (2001). In previous studies, scientists' theoretical models and findings suggest that emotions may very much influence cognitive and strategic decisions (Lewis et al., 2009) for a review see and that different emotions have different effects (Lerner et al., 2000). While previous research has shown that emotion is one of the fundamental elements of human inner feelings and experiences, the new cognitive revolution in psychology has simultaneously marginalized the study of emotion. However, affective trust manifests itself slightly differently at different stages, but all influence the consumer's next action.

2.1.2 Cognitive involvement

Cognitive involvement is a prerequisite for consumers to purchase items. Cognitive involvement has been used to study stimulus consumers' purchases (Zaichkowsky, 1986). Researchers have extended range of application of cognitive involvement to shopping platforms (McMillan et al., 2003; Cho, 1999). The cognitive involvement construct been discussed and studied in previous literature on consumer behavior (Liu & Shrum, 2002; O'Cass, 2000). Three main antecedents of cognitive involvement are mentioned in Zaichkowsky (1986). Relating to the people's characteristics is the first factor, relating to the trait of the stimulus is the second factor, and relating to the trait of the situation is the third factor. The study's definition cognitive involvement as the relevance of consumers in conjunction with their own needs, values and interests. Also, the two aspects of cognitive involvement are affective involvement and cognitive involvement. Cognitive engagement is enhanced when consumers are exposed to cues from the shopping platform during their interactions with it (Eroglu et al., 2003). These leads help consumers to achieve Their shopping targets, which are their utilitarian motivations (Babin et al., 1994). The simultaneous the study of cognitive and affective metrics of website involvement yields insightful information into the different internal consumer processes in two crucial psychological aspects. Existing research suggests that interactions with shopping platforms elicit both cognitive and affective influences within consumers (Koufaris, 2002; Eroglu et al., 2003). Cognitive engagement is associated with "rational thinking" and is caused by utilitarian or cognitive motivations. This suggests that consumers' cognitive involvement is a combination of affective and cognitive (Park & Young, 1986). These functions improve the aesthetic and experience value of shopping on a shopping platform (Babin et al., 1994; Mathwick et al., 2001).

2.1.3 Functional value

Functional value is an important determinant of consumers' choice of goods. Consumers are considered as logical thinkers who use deliberative thinking to select the finest product from the available choices based on an assessment of the product's functional value (Shafir et al., 1993). The influence of the experiential consumption perspective that current marketing literature evidence implies that firms or shopping platforms Experiential value is another possibility (Brakus et al., 2009; Chang & Chieng, 2006; Schembri, 2009; Zarantonello et al., 2013). Functional value is related to the ability to satisfy consumers' functional needs and desires (Keller, 2001). This perspective includes the assessment of the functional experiential benefits that result from the purchase and consumption activities. The experiential characteristics of consumers are the primary source of subjective, internal consumer responses (sensory, emotional, and cognitive) other behavioral reactions to their functionality that can offer useful experiential value in their own right (Brakus et al., 2009). The current tendency in marketing literature is to create captivating brand experiences by highlighting non-functional product characteristics. such as merchandise-related stimuli as well as packaging, communication, and merchandising/sales-related design elements. The functional experiential value of the merchandise refers to the subjectivity, symbolism, hedonics, and psychology of interaction with the merchandise (Hirschman & Holbrook, 1982). It reflects the evaluation of various functional experiences of consumers with goods, which Brakus et al. (2009) categorize as sensory organs (e.g., feelings), emotional perceptions (e.g., sensations, and emotions), and functional consumer values as behaviors (e.g., physical experiences, behaviors, and lifestyles).

2.1.4 Personality Traits

Personality traits can largely influence a consumer's choice habits. The theory of personality traits was developed Carlyle (1841) and later refined continuously by Allport (1937), who was famous as the dispositional personality trait approach and described personality traits as a disposition towards life experiences. Proponents of personality trait theory commonly list managerial qualities in relation to effective managerial behavior in the workplace. Kirkpatrick and Locke (1996) describe personality trait theory in the management concept as motivation, including a wide range of attributes of motivation, energy, resourcefulness, and accomplishment. Allport, Eysenck, and Cattell are the founders of personality trait theory in psychology

(Matthews et al., 2003). Eysenck (1967) proposed a spectrum of three personality traits, specifically neuroticism and extraversion, and psychopathy. These elements were measured by means of self-report. The author presented the three-factor personality model's higher-order dimensions. Cattell (1973) argued that there are 16 personality elements. His seminal study of personality is very noteworthy in psychology. It pursued explanations for differences in all aspects of a person's life from psychological measures of cognitive ability, motivation, personality, and disposition. The primary focus of personality trait theorists is the examination of personality traits, often known as habitual patterns. behavior, reasoning ability, and emotion. Trait theorists believe that there are two different key beliefs that go into the formation of each personality trait. The first assumption is that traits influence behavior. If a person unexpectedly brands himself or herself in a good mental state, one can describe a manish situation in which the individual is in a happy state. This claim is certainly based on instability due to its circular nature (Smillie et al., 2012). The second argues that personality traits are constant throughout time. It is intuitively comprehensible that a person's behavior varies over time, but insists that there is critical stability that explains a person's true nature, i.e., the constant sign of the leopard (Smillie, 2013) In other words, there are visible differences between individuals across several events and occasions.

2.1.5 Purchase intention

Purchase intention is a consumer's inclination towards a good. Purchase intention is a planned decision that examines the reasons why consumers buy a particular good (Shah et al., 2012). The defines purchase intention as a consumer's tendency to buy a certain product under certain conditions. According to Khraim (2011), customers' purchase intention is influenced by many factors. The study by Kawa et al. (2013) shows that packaging has a significant effect on customer's purchase intention. A customer's decision to purchase an item is a difficult process. Purchase intention is usually related to the consumer's perceptions and attitudes. Purchase behavior is the key place where consumers acquire and evaluate a specific good. Koshazadeh et al. (2012) concluded in their research indicates that the visual and functional components of packaging can influence consumers' purchase intention towards food products (Deng, 2009). Ghosh (1990) stated that consumers' purchase intention is a very effective tool for forecasting their purchase process. Consumers are influenced based on internal or external forces in the

process of shopping for goods. As argued by Cahyorini and Rusfian (2012), this aspect can have a significant instantaneous impact on customers' purchase intentions since consumers' purchase intentions are influenced by the appearance of the goods in unplanned purchases, especially in terms of packaging. That is, it is a cognitive engagement behavior of consumers regarding its functional value, etc.

2.2 Related Literature Review

2.2.1 emotional trust and purchase intention

In the process of online shopping, emotional trust is an important influence on consumers' intention to purchase a product. Therefore, the formation of trust has a direct and positive impact on intention. Harrison et al. (2002) argues that consumers' purchase behavior in online shopping platforms is one of the various behavioral intentions induced by trust (Harrison et al., 2002). Both emotional trust and cognitive trust fall under the category of trust. The Affective Trust and Purchase Intention scales in Teng and Wang (2015) also indicate an interaction between the two. There is an interactive relationship between affective trust and purchase intention as it is correlated (Nuttavuthisit & Thogersen, 2017). The latter adds directly to marketing efforts since it shows consumers' future purchase intentions or willingness to purchase a product (Hemmerling et al., 2015). For affective trust and purchase intention, the same structure of Sweeney and Soutar (2001) is also verified.

2.2.2 Personality trait and Purchase intention

Consumer personality has a positive impact on consumer choice or behavior related to online shopping (Punj & Stewart, 1983; Bosnjak et al., 2007). Personality factors, such as being imaginative, reliable, charismatic, etc., influence consumers' evaluation of goods and thus their purchase intention (Khare et al., 2010). Purchase intention is the probability, likelihood and willingness of a consumer to purchase a product or it may be the consumer's plan to purchase a product (Dodds et al., 1991). Customer's personality traits influence their intention to purchase an item, based on customer loyalty, etc., and the intention to recommend it to others (Sirohi et al., 1998). (1) Consumers' purchase intention is influenced by consumers' own personality traits. Customers' actions and behavior toward a product are referred to as "loyalty," and include things like repeat purchases and recommending the product to others. (2) Switching: refers to consumers choosing the product less in favor of their rival's product; (3) Overpayment: consumers choosing the product even though the price of the product has increased; (4) External reaction: refers to

consumers choosing the product less in favor of their rival product. External reaction: refers to consumers who report dissatisfaction with a product or service to a third party other than the firm. Customers who are unsatisfied with a product or service and report it to the company's workers constitute an internal reaction (Zeithaml et al., 1996). Customers' personality traits influence their intention to purchase a particular item, based on customer loyalty, etc., and their intention to recommend it to others (Sirohi et al., 1998).

2.2.3 Personality trait and Emotional trust

Personality traits affect consumers' emotional trust in goods or certain product services to some extent. There are relatively few studies on the impact of personality traits on trust in HRM (Hancock et al., 2011; Lewis et al., 2009). There is some uncertainty in the relationship between personality traits and trust, requiring further research of sufficient theoretical and methodological quality to provide insight into the practical impact of personality factors on trust in management. To this end, the contrast between dispositional personality traits and trusting attitudes serves as the hypothesis' starting point. According to Ajzen (2005), the concepts of traits and trusting attitudes have significant similarities, while differing in terms of stability and focus, so that there is some relationship between the influence of personality traits on trust. Personality traits refer to "reaction tendencies in a specific domain" Ajzen (2005) and are not oriented towards a specific object. Instead, reaction tendencies include trust or distrust of something, etc.

2.2.4 Cognitive involvement and Purchase intention

Cognitive involvement has a strong relationship with consumers' purchase intention. It is now considered imperative to assess customer engagement in order to understand and predict consumer's online shopping behavior (Hong, 2015; Demoulin & Willems, 2019). Huang (2012) showed that affective and cognitive engagement influence consumer's purchase intention have shown that consumer engagement is positively related to attitudes toward the product or shopping site, which in turn affects consumers' intention to make purchases from shopping platforms (Jiang et al., 2010). In low cognitive engagement with a shopping site, consumers do not have access to valuable product information that matches their own, which may lead to lower purchase intentions to purchase the product. The contrast between dispositional personality traits and trusting attitudes serves as the hypothesis' starting point. It has been shown that consumers' cognitive state affects shopping outcomes i.e. consumers' willingness to purchase intention (Eroglu et al., 2003). Emotional

engagement describes the high level of emotional cognition associated with a website that allows consumers to have a better positive intention (Jiang et al., 2010). Positive cognitive states include happiness and satisfaction, which may lead to higher purchase intentions within the consumer's shopping platform. A person's desire to shop on the platform may be diminished if they are experiencing unpleasant emotions such as rage or disappointment.

2.2.5 Functional value and Purchase intention

The functional value of goods can largely influence consumers' purchase intention. According to functional value can influence the shopping efficiency of consumers, that is, the rate at which consumers can obtain the desired value from the goods' home province. In the words of Long and Schiffman (2000), The intrinsic value of a product or service is used to calculate functional value, rather than any extrinsic value. Therefore, consumers focus on the functional value of a good when choosing it. It has been noted that online sales make consumers feel more convenient (Chang & Wang, 2011) and time-saving (Lee & Ndubisi, 2011) when compared to traditional shopping methods in terms of obtaining the desired product or service because consumers can clearly perceive it through the platform in terms of functional value. And because of the efficiency and effectiveness of consumers' purchases in online shopping platforms, there is an enhanced value in terms of functional value of goods compared to traditional shopping methods (Pavlou, 2003). So, in a similar way, Engström et al. (2015) illustrates that functional value contributes differently to consumers' choices. For some time, one of the key influences in consumer choice has been considered to be functional value (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001).

2.3 Conceptual Framework

In this study, the researcher constructs the conceptual frame based on three previous theoretical frameworks. The first theoretical framework is from the article "Research on the Relationship between Online Reviews and Customer Purchase Intention: The Moderating Role of Personality Trait" by Tian et al. (2014). This study provides information about the relationship between purchase intention and affective trust and personality traits. As well as the relationship between affective trust, cognitive trust, review motivation, check quality, check quantity, and purchase intention. The study shows that there are many factors that influence purchase intention. The second theoretical framework from the article "Effects of Interactivity on Website Involvement and Purchase Intention by Jiang et al. (2010). The third

theoretical framework from the article “The Effects of Online Shopping Context Cues on Consumers’ Purchase Intention for Cross-Border E-Commerce Sustainability” by Xiao et al. (2019). This study looks at online promotions, content marketing, personalized

recommendations, social commentary, functional value. Emotional value, and brand familiarity to explore the factors that influence purchase intention. Therefore, the conceptual framework has been presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The conceptual framework of the effecting factors of personality trait and shopping attribute on emotional trust and purchase intention: a case study of PinDuoDuo e-Commerce in China.

The hypotheses in this study have been formulated as presented below.

Hypothesis 1 (H1): There is a significant effect of personality traits on emotional trust.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): There is a significant effect of personality traits on purchase intention.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): There is a significant effect of emotional trust on purchase intention.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): There is a significant effect of cognitive involvement on purchase intention

Hypothesis 5 (H5): There is a significant effect of functional value on purchase intention

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The purpose of this study is to determine the factors that influence consumer purchase intention related to emotional trust, personality traits, cognitive engagement, and functional value. In addition, this study will explore the extent to which each variable affects consumer purchase intention. Since this paper is a quantitative study, there are several analytical methods such as Cronbach's Alpha, multiple linear regression, simple linear regression, and descriptive data study.

The questionnaire consisted of three parts, of which 24 items were related to the four variables of the research model, three items were related to the screening questions, 17 items were related to the measurement variables, and four items were related to demographic information. First, Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the questionnaire's reliability and whether there was uncertainty or confusion regarding the items

being measured. A pilot test was conducted with a small sample of 85 individuals to verify the reliability of the questionnaire and to check for confusion in the items measured in the questionnaire. In this study, the researchers used a five-point Likert scale to assess respondents' attitudes and their level of agreement based on each variable. The statistical level was set at 1 for "strongly disagree" and 5 for "strongly agree". Next, the researchers used multiple linear regression (MLR) to analyze the factors influencing consumers' purchase intention as emotional trust, cognitive engagement, and functional value. In addition, the researchers still used simple linear regression (SLR) to analyze the effect of personality traits on affective trust and purchase intention.

3.2 Sampling Plan

3.2.1 Target population

In this study, the target population is Chinese consumers who have had experience shopping online on the Pound land platform. Therefore, the study will use a target population as 869 million (as of March 21, 2022).

3.2.2 Sampling size

In this study, the authors used Cochran's formula to calculate the sample size. Since this formula is used to calculate the sample size without knowing the size of the population. In order to determine the necessary survey size for an unknown population, at 95% confidence level, 50% standard deviation, and 5% margin of error, $z = 1.96$. The following formula is used to calculate the sample size.

$$n = \frac{[z^2 * p * (1 - p) / e^2] / [1 + (z^2 * p * (1 - p) / (e^2 * N))]}{}$$

Where: z = 1.96 for a confidence level (α) of 95%,

p = proportion (expressed as a decimal),

N = population size,

e = margin of error.

z = 1.96, p = 0.5, N = 868700000, e = 0.05

$$n = \frac{[1.962 * 0.5 * (1 - 0.5) / 0.052] / [1 + (1.962 * 0.5 * (1 - 0.5) / (0.052 * 868700000))]}{}$$

$$n = 384.16 / 1 = 384.16, n \approx 385$$

Sample size equal to 385

3.2.3 Sampling procedure

In this study, non-probability sampling methods be used, including nonrandom selection based on convenience and ease of data collection. The researcher chose Methods of convenience sampling and snowball sampling to collect information because of the priority of screening respondents according to the study objectives. The researcher chose to make use of non-probability sampling method in the study because of the need to maintain some distance from the community due to time and identity constraints. Therefore, this method is appropriate and the researcher can easily collect data at a convenient condition.

3.3 Validity

3.3.1 Content validation using the item-objective congruence index

The authors used the Index of Item-Objective Congruence on this questionnaire to determine whether item quality was up to par for each question in the

Table 1. Pilot Test Results – Cronbach’s Alpha

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items	The power of the association
Emotional trust	0.796	4	Acceptable
Cognitive involvement	0.838	4	Good
Functional value	0.806	3	Good
Personality trait	0.780	3	Acceptable
Purchase intention	0.882	3	Good

4. Results

4.1 Reliability Testing

The researchers decided to identify any inconsistent or incorrect variables again for all 410 respondents' questionnaires. Test of Cronbach's Alpha dependability was used to assess and analyze the consistency of the questionnaires. Table 2 shows that the authors Cronbach's Alpha was utilized to measure the scale of reliability The SPSS program was used to determine the closeness a collection of stuff as a group. Results The

questionnaire. The authors sought expert opinion to determine the content validity score. For the IOC value, the result was 0.67. Since the result was greater than 0.5, all questions were suitable for distribution to the respondents.

3.4.2 Reliability of the pilot test

The researcher selected 85 participants for a pilot study with the Cronbach's Alpha test to identify any inconsistent or incorrect variables in the questionnaire. Cronbach's Alpha is used to assess the reliability of any given measured variable. Consistency is measured by Cronbach's Alpha. According to Peter (1979), a well-known indicator for measuring and testing research reliability is Cronbach's Alpha. If the value of Cronbach's Alpha is greater than 0.6; this means that the researcher can accept that Cronbach's Alpha is reliable. The results of analysis in study indicate level of Cronbach's Alpha as display in the Table 1 below.

Tables 1 statistic the authors used Cronbach's Alpha, an program that measures the reliability of a scale to determine the closeness of a set of items. The results show that the overall variables affecting consumer purchase intention consist of four items. The results showed that Cronbach's alpha was 0.796 for four items of emotional trust, 0.828 for four items of cognitive involvement, 0.806 for three items of functional value, and 0.780 for three items of personality traits for three items of purchase intention. all the factors affecting consumer purchase intention were above 0.6, which means that they are reliable!
(n = 85)

results show that the total variables of factors that affect consumer purchase intention consisted of five items. The results revealed that all variables were reliable and valid, as the values were greater than 0.8, indicating good reliability of all factors. The highest reliability was Emotional trust reliability of 0.807 for 4 items, followed by Cognitive involvement reliability of 0.817 for 4 items, Personality trait of 0.853 for 3 items, Functional value of 0.817 for 3 items, and finally Purchase intention of 3 items was 0.873!

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha*(n=410)*

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Quantity of Items	Result
Emotional trust	0.807	4	Reliable
Cognitive involvement	0.817	4	Reliable
Functional value	0.853	3	Reliable
Personality trait	0.817	3	Reliable
Purchase intention	0.873	3	Reliable

4.2 Descriptive analysis of demographic data

The authors used descriptive analysis in the program to analyze the demographic information of the current Chinese respondents. Demographic information, such as gender, age, highest education, and monthly income, is available and the authors use descriptive analysis, elucidate the traits of the respondents. Table 3 shows the frequency distribution and percentages of the 410 respondents as follows. **Gender:** out of all 410 respondents, their distribution shows a higher percentage of males at 50.73%, which is higher than the female respondents at 49.27%. The percentage of males was 50.73%, higher than the 49.27% of female respondents. The results for males and females were 208 and 202, respectively. **Age:** In this study, the largest number of respondents were between 26-35 years old with 118 respondents or 28.78%, followed by respondents between 18-25 years old with 104 respondents or

25.37%, between 46-55 years old with 80 respondents or 19.58%, between 36-45 years old with 77 respondents or 18.78%, and the fewest number of respondents aged 55 or older, 31 or 7.56%. **Education level:** Among the 410 respondents, 145 respondents received a bachelor's degree (35.37%), followed by 136 respondents (33.17%) who received a high school degree, 69 respondents received a master's degree (16.83%); 45 respondents were below a high school degree, accounting for 10.98%, and the last 15 respondents had a doctoral or higher degree, with a percentage of 3.66%. **Monthly income:** Most of the respondents who participated in the survey had a monthly income of RMB 3,000-8,000 with 150 people or 36.59%; followed by a monthly income of RMB 8,000-12,000 with 120 people or 29.27%; a monthly income of more than RMB 12,000 with 74 people or 18.05%; a monthly income of less than RMB 3,000 with 66 people or 16.1%.

Table 3. Analysis of demographic factors using frequency distributions and percentages*(n=410)*

The demographics	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	208	50.73
Female	202	49.27
Total	410	100
Age (Years)		
18 – 25 years old	104	25.37
26 – 35 years old	118	28.78
36 – 45 years old	77	18.78
46 – 55 years old	80	19.51
Over 55 years old	31	7.56
Total	410	100
Education Level		
Lower than high school	45	10.98
High school	136	33.17
Bachelor's Degree	145	35.37
Master's Degree	69	16.83
Ph. D. Degree or higher	15	3.66
Total	410	100
Income per month		
Less than 3000 RMB	66	16.10
3000-8000 RMB	150	36.59
8000- 12,000 RMB	120	29.27
More than 12,000 RMB	74	18.05
Total	410	100

4.3 Descriptive Analysis of Means and Standard Deviations

In this section, we analyze the means and standard deviations of each group of variables (including affective trust, cognitive involvement, personality traits, functional value, and purchase intention) as follows. Table 4 shows that the maximum average of Emotional trust is "I believe the e-commerce platforms before I buy the product from e-commerce platforms", equal to 4.03; "When I shop for a product, I will pay attention to whether it has any negative news so that I can trust it", equal to 3.96; "I will choose those products with good reviews" equal to 3.96; However, the lowest average is "If my friends around me trust this product, I will also choose to try to buy it", equal to 3.94. In terms of standard deviation, the highest "When I shop for a product, I will pay attention to whether it has any negative news so that I can trust it. The result is 1.144; On the other hand, the lowest "I trust the e-commerce platforms before I buy the product from e-commerce platforms", equal to 1.08.

Table 4 shows that the highest mean value of Cognitive involvement is "I will buy the product only if I think it will be useful to me in ecommerce platforms." The result is 4.01, and the lowest average is "I will only buy products that I know about in e-commerce platforms", its mean value is 3.92. In terms of standard deviation, the highest "I will buy the product if someone introduces it to me in e-commerce platforms", equal to 1.156. On the other hand, the lowest "I will buy the product only if

I think it will be useful to me in ecommerce platforms", equal to 1.097.

Table 4 shows, Greatest average value of Functional value "I will buy products with more functional value in e-commerce platforms" The result is 4.02; and the lowest average is "I will only buy products that have features I can use, in e-commerce platforms", Equivalent to 3.91. For standard deviation, the highest "I will only buy products that have features I can use, in e-commerce platforms." The result is 1.166. The lowest is "I will buy products with more functional value in e-commerce platforms", equal to 1.119.

Table 4 shows the greatest average value of Personality trait "I always buy products according to my persona", Its mean value is 3.97, while the lowest mean value is "I like to try new things and products, so I am willing to buy new products in e-commerce platforms", equal to 3.95. In terms of standard deviation, the highest "I like to have a look at the detail of product with others' comments and then buy the product in e-commerce platforms", equal to 1.166. On the other hand, the lowest "I like to try new things and products, so I am willing to buy new products in e-commerce platforms", its standard deviation is 1.150.

Table 4 shows, purchase intention, the mean values of the three items were equal, the results were both 3.93. In terms of the average deviation, the greatest is "I am planning to buy products on e-commerce platforms", equal to 1.187, On the other hand, the lowest "I intend to buy products on ecommerce platforms now", equal to 1.092.

Table 4. The results of Mean and Standard Deviation

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Emotional trust			
ET1: If my friends around me trust this product, I will also choose to try to buy it.	410	3.94	1.128
ET2: I will choose those products with good reviews.	410	3.96	1.137
ET3: When I shop for a product, I will pay attention to whether it has any negative news so that I can trust it.	410	3.96	1.144
ET4: I trust the e-commerce platforms before I buy the product from e-commerce platforms.	410	4.03	1.055
Cognitive involvement			
CI1: I will only buy products that I know about in e-commerce platforms.	410	3.92	1.124
CI2: I will check the information before I buy the product in e-commerce platforms.	410	3.95	1.121
CI3: I will buy the product if someone introduces it to me in e-commerce platforms.	410	3.98	1.156
CI4: I will buy the product only if I think it will be useful to me in ecommerce	410	4.01	1.097

platforms.			
Functional value			
FV1: I will only buy products that have features I can use, in e-commerce platforms.	410	3.91	1.166
FV2: I think a good product is one that satisfies the needs of customer in ecommerce platforms.	410	3.94	1.160
FV3: I will buy products with more functional value in e-commerce platforms.	410	4.02	1.119
Personality traits			
PT1: I like to have a look at the detail of product with others' comments and then buy the product in e-commerce platforms.	410	3.96	1.166
PT2: I like to try new things and products, so I am willing to buy new products in e-commerce platforms	410	3.95	1.150
PT3: I always buy products according to my personal preference in e-commerce platforms.	410	3.97	1.164
Purchase intention			
PI1: I will seriously be buying products from e-commerce platforms.	410	3.93	1.172
PI2: I am planning to buy products on e-commerce platforms.	410	3.93	1.187
PI3: I intend to buy products on ecommerce platforms now.	410	3.93	1.092

4.4 Hypothesis Testing Results

4.4.1 Summary of Simple Linear Regression of H1

Tables 5 show simple linear regressions were conducted to determine if personality traits significantly predicted affective trust. The results of hypothesis 1 reject the null hypothesis and also show the results of the regression. The model is significant and the model explains 30.0% of the variance, $F=174.627$, $p<.05$. R^2 was .300 at the 95% confidence level. the results showed that personality traits ($\beta=.547$, $p<.05$) had a positive significance on affective trust.

Hypothesis 1

Table 5. Summary of simple linear regression analysis for Hypothesis 1

Variables	B	SE B	β	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.030	0.151		13.407	0.000
Personality traits	0.490	0.037	0.547	13.215	0.000*

Note. $R^2= .300$, Adjusted $R^2= .298$, $*p < .05$. Dependent Variable = Emotional trust

4.4.2 Summary of Simple Linear Regression of H2

Tables 6 show a simple linear regression was conducted to determine if personality traits significantly predicted purchase intention. Hypothesis 2 showed that the null hypothesis was rejected. The results of the regression showed that the model explained 27.5% of the Variations and the model was significant. So, $F=154.440$, $p<.05$. R^2 was .275 at the 95% confidence level. the results showed that personality traits ($\beta=.524$, $p<.05$) had a positive significance on purchase intention.

Hypothesis 2

H1o: Personality trait has no significant effect on emotional trust on online shopping platforms.

H1a: Personality trait has a significant effect on emotional trust on online shopping platforms.

Tables 5 show a significant level of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. The blanket hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, we can conclude that affective trust is influenced by personality traits. Moreover, the standardized coefficient of personality traits is 0.547. This means that if personality traits increase by 1%, affective trust can increase by 54.7%!.

H2o: Personality trait has no significant effect on purchase intention in online shopping platforms.

H2a: Personality trait has a significant effect on purchase intention in online shopping platforms.

Table 6 shows a significant level of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. The blanket hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, we can conclude that purchase intention is influenced by personality traits. Moreover, the standardized coefficient of personality traits is 0.524. This means that if personality traits increase by 1%, purchase intention can increase by 52.4%!.

Table 6. Summary of Simple Linear Regression Analysis for Hypothesis 2

Variables	B	SE B	β	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.780	0.178		9.991	0.000
Personality traits	0.543	0.044	0.524	12.427	0.000*

Note. $R^2 = .275$, Adjusted $R^2 = .273$, $*p < .05$. Dependent Variable = Purchase intention

4.4.3 Summary of multiple linear regression of H3, H4, and H5

In this section, the authors used multiple linear regression to predict the extent to which affective trust, cognitive engagement, and functional value influence consumer purchase intention.

Tables 7 show that multiple linear regressions were conducted to determine if affective trust, cognitive engagement, and functional value significantly predicted purchase intention. The results for hypotheses 3, 4, and 5 show that all independent variables used to determine the effect on purchase intention did not overlap and there was no multicollinearity because the VIF was less than 5. The VIF for emotional trust was 1.034, for cognitive involvement was 1.058, and for functional value was 1.051. In addition, the R-square was 0.475 at the 95% confidence level. This implies that the independent variables (emotional trust, cognitive involvement, and functional value) can justify approximately 47.5% of the dependent variable (purchase intention). The results show that 47.5% of the variance in purchase intention can be explained by three predictors. Combined $F=122.393$, $p<.05$. By looking at the individual contribution of each predictor, the results showed that affective trust ($\beta = .379$, $p<.05$), cognitive involvement ($\beta = .329$, $p<.05$) and functional value ($\beta = .332$, $p<.05$) had a positive effect on purchase intention.

Hypothesis 3

H3o: Emotional trust has no significant effect on purchase intention in online shopping platforms.

H3a: Emotional trust has a significant effect on purchase intention in online shopping platforms.

Table 7 shows that the significance level coefficient is 0.000 and the value is inferior to 0.05. The null hypothesis is unaccepted, so it can be said that emotional

trust has a substantial impact on purchase intention. Moreover, emotional trust is the parameter that has the greatest impact on purchase intention with the highest value of the standardized coefficient of 0.379. This means that if emotional trust the increase is 1%, purchase intention may grow by 379.9% year-on-year.

Hypothesis 4

H4o: Cognitive involvement has no significant effect on purchase intention in online shopping platforms.

H4a: Cognitive involvement has a significant effect on purchase intention in online shopping platforms.

Tables 7 show that the significance level is 0.000 and the simultaneous value lower than 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected, so It can be said that cognitive involvement has a significant effect on purchase intention. In addition, cognitive involvement is the variable that has an impact on purchase intention with a standardized coefficient value of 0.329. This means that if cognitive involvement increase is 1%, purchase intention can increase by 32.9% year-on-year.

Hypothesis 5

H5o: Functional value has no significant effect on purchase intention in online shopping platforms.

H5a: Functional value has no significant effect on purchase intention in online shopping platforms.

Table 7 shows that the value of significance level is 0.000 and the value is inferior to 0.05, rejecting the null hypothesis, then It can be said that functional value has a significant effect on purchase intention. In addition, functional value is the variable that has an effect on purchase intention with a standardized coefficient value of 0.332. This means that if functional value increase is 1%, purchase intention can increase by 33.2% year-on-year.

Table 7. Summary of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis for Hypotheses 3, 4, and 5

Variables	B	SE B	β	t	Sig.	VIF
(Constant)	-.632	0.241		-2.620	0.000	
Emotional trust	0.438	0.042	0.379	10.351	0.000*	1.034
Cognitive involvement	0.375	0.042	0.329	8.904	0.000*	1.058
Functional value	0.338	0.038	0.332	9.003	0.000*	1.051

Note. $R^2 = .475$, Adjusted $R^2 = .471$, $*p < .05$. Dependent Variable = Purchase intention

Figure 2. The result of structural model

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1 Summary of the study

The summary of the study was based on a research objective to precisely examine the relationships of those variables that affects purchase intention. The factors of interest in the study were emotional trust, personality fitness, cognitive involvement, and functional value. The question that guided this study were; (1) does personality traits have a significant effect in emotional trust?(2) does personality traits have a significant effect in purchase intention? (3) does emotional trust have a significant effect in purchase intention? (4) does cognitive involvement have a significant effect in purchase intention? (5) does functional value have a significant effect in purchase intention? A descriptive research design was used in this study. The study focused on Chinese online shopping consumers who shopped on the Jindo online shopping platform. The population of the study was consumers of the Jindo online shopping platform. Therefore, the researchers used the equation by Cochran (1997) to calculate the sample size. By using convenience sampling and snowball sampling, using

non-probability sampling, a sample size of 385 respondents was selected. However, of these 385 targets, 410 responded to the questionnaire used for data collection. To ensure consistency and reliability, closed-ended questions were used in the structured questionnaire. The collected data were transformed into raw data, analyzed using the program, and presented using figures and tables. Descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation, and frequency were used to analyze the collected data. Inferential analyses of association and regression were also used in the study to provide insight into the variables. The authors used multiple and simple linear regression for hypothesis inspection. Simple linear regression was used to determine the degree of influence between affective trust, purchase intention, and personality traits. Multiple linear regression was used to determine the extent to which affective trust, cognitive involvement, and functional value influenced purchase intention. The results of the hypothesis testing showed that all four independent variables were rejected and were statistically significant. The results of the hypothesis testing are as follows (Table 8).

Table 8. Summary results from the hypotheses testing

Hypotheses	Significant Value	Standardized Coefficient	Result
H1o: Personality trait has no significant effect on emotional trust on online shopping platforms.	0.000*	0.547	Rejected
H2o: Personality trait has no significant effect on purchase intention in online shopping platforms.	0.000*	0.524	Rejected
H3o: Emotional trust has no significant effect on purchase intention in online shopping platforms.	0.000*	0.379	Rejected
H4o: Cognitive involvement has no significant effect on purchase intention in online shopping platforms.	0.000*	0.329	Rejected
H5o: Functional value has no significant effect on purchase intention in online shopping platforms.	0.000*	0.332	Rejected

Note. *P-value <0.05

The results of hypothesis testing using multiple and simple linear regressions show the dominance of factors that influence the variables of consumer purchase intention. It shows that the most important factor influencing consumer purchase intention is personality traits. The ranking results of the hypothesis tests are summarized in the table below.

Table 9 displays the order of the effects of emotional trust, cognitive involvement, and functional value on

purchase intention from the most significant to the least significant. The beta value is used in the research to measure the connection between the fluctuating independence and dependence. The results show that the independent variable most closely related to purchase intention is personality trait 0.379, which means that for every 1 unit increase in emotional trust, purchase intention increases by 0.379, followed by functional value 0.332, then cognitive involvement 0.329.

Table 9. Strengths of factor influence of variable to Purchase intention

Rank	Independent Variable	Beta
1 st	Emotional trust	0.379
2 nd	Functional value	0.332
3 rd	Cognitive involvement	0.329

The effect of emotional trust on purchase intention. In the study, beta values were used to measure the association between factors as independent and dependent. The results showed that the beta value for the independent variable emotional trust was 0.379, which means that for every 1 unit increase in personality traits, emotional trust increased by 0.379. For every 1 unit increase in cognitive engagement, purchase intention increases by 0.332. For every 1 unit increase in

functional value, the purchase intention increases by 0.332.

Table 10 shows the significance of personality traits and purchase intention in the simple linear regression analysis. Beta values were used in the study to measure the association between independence of fluctuations and dependence. The results show that the independent variable most strongly associated with purchase intention was personality trait 0.379.

Table 10. Strengths of factor influence of variable to Purchase intention

Independent Variable	Beta
Personality trait	0.524

The effect of personality traits on purchase intention. In the study, beta values were used to measure the association between the factors that were the independent and dependent variables. The results showed that the beta value for the independent variable personality trait was 0.524, which means that for every 1 unit increase in personality trait, purchase intention increased by 0.524.

Table 11 shows the significance of personality traits and Emotional trust in the simple linear regression analysis. Beta values were used in the study to measure the association between independence of fluctuations and dependence. The results show that the independent variable most strongly associated with Emotional trust was personality trait 0.547.

Table 11. Strengths of factor influence of variable to Emotional trust

Independent Variable	Beta
Personality trait	0.547

The effect of personality traits on Emotional trust. In the study, beta values were used to measure the association between the factors that were the independent and dependent variables. The results showed that the beta value for the independent variable personality trait was 0.547, which means that for every 1 unit increase in personality trait, Emotional trust increased by 0.547.

5.2 Discussion and Conclusion

Hypothesis testing showed that four variables, namely personality traits, affective trust, cognitive involvement and functional value, influence consumer purchase intention, while personality traits are also factors that influence affective trust. The four factors, namely personality traits, affective trust, cognitive involvement

and functional value, have a significant effect on consumers' purchase intention. Personality traits also have a significant effect on affective trust.

5.2.1 Personality trait and Emotional trust

This study shows that personality traits be constructive and highly major connection to affective trust. The significant value of personality traits and affective trust was 0.000. This means that the consistency of firms in targeting personality traits will contribute significantly to gaining consumers' affective trust. This is consistent with the view that a person's personality traits affect his emotional trust to some extent. When their personality traits are not met, they exhibit emotional behaviors of distrust. Through an in-depth descriptive analysis of the three questions in the questionnaire we collected, the statistics show that the mean value of personality traits was 3.96. Among all the questions, the lowest mean was " I like to try new things and products, so I am willing to buy new products in e-commerce platforms ", equal to 3.95, below average.

5.2.2 Personality trait and Purchase intention

This study showed that personality traits have a positive and significant relationship with purchase intention. The significant value for motivation and job satisfaction was 0.000. This study is in line with Kao (2017) study that motivational personality traits affect their purchase intention and that a willingness to try new things increases their purchase intention. The study shows that familiarity with customer personality traits can help increase customers' intention to buy a company's products. The mastery of personality traits brings more benefits in terms of achieving increased consumer purchase intentions. The greatest average value of Personality trait "I always buy products according to my persona", Its mean value is 3.97, while the lowest mean value is " I like to try new things and products, so I am willing to buy new products in e-commerce platforms ", equal to 3.95. In terms of standard deviation, the highest " I like to have a look at the detail of product with others' comments and then buy the product in e-commerce platforms", equal to 1.166. On the other hand, the lowest " I like to try new things and products, so I am willing to buy new products in e-commerce platforms ", Its standard deviation is 1.150.

Therefore, companies should develop sales strategies that target the personality traits of their customers, for example, in the feedback channels of their products, and learn more about the personality traits of their users so that they can develop the next step of their product production and sales strategies.

5.2.3 Emotional trust and Purchase intention

This study shows that emotional trust has a positive and highly significant relationship with purchase intention. The significant value of emotional trust and purchase intention was 0.000, which means that it is crucial for companies to maintain and improve the consistency of emotional trust among their customers to increase their purchase intention. Furthermore, the results of this study are consistent with the study of Watanabe et al. (2019). The study showed that emotional trust positively affects consumers' purchase intention. Through an in-depth descriptive analysis of the emotional trust of the four questions in the questionnaire we collected, the statistics showed a mean value of 3.97 for job satisfaction. The highest standard deviation is from the standard deviation of the largest problem is " When I shop for a product, I will pay attention to whether it has any negative news so that I can trust it. ", The standard deviation is 1.144, Secondly " I will choose those products with good reviews. " The standard deviations are both 1.137 and then " If my friends around me trust this product, I will also choose to try to buy it.", Its standard deviation is 1.128, And finally "I trust the e-commerce platforms before I buy the product from e-commerce platforms." The standard deviation is 1.055. By way of results, the company should find a way to gain the emotional trust of the consumer, such as providing proof of safe products and examples to gain the trust of the consumer so that they choose the product. Or do more charity work.

5.2.4 Cognitive involvement and Purchase intention

This study shows that cognitive involvement has a positive and highly significant relationship with purchase intention. The significant value of cognitive involvement and purchase intention was 0.000. This means that consumers' perception of the product has a substantial effect on their purchase intention. The present study is compatible with Jiang et al. (2010) believe there is a favorable connection between cognitive engagement and purchase intention. The results of our descriptive analysis of motivation collected from the closed-ended questionnaire showed that the mean of cognitive engagement from the four questions was 3.965. the lowest mean of the three questions was " I will only buy products that I know about in e-commerce platforms. ", The average was 3.92. In addition, "I will buy the product if someone introduces it to me in e-commerce platforms." This question had the highest standard deviation of 1.156. Therefore, companies should consider improving consumer awareness participation and increasing consumer involvement in the shopping process, such as providing product stands and actively answering

consumer questions, thereby enhancing consumer involvement and boosting their purchase intentions.

5.2.5 Functional value and Purchase intention

In this research, there was a very high significant relationship between functional value and purchase intention. The significant value of functional value and purchase intention is 0.000. This means that functional value has a significant effect on purchase intention. In the present study the results were consistent with that study of Ramayah et al. (2016) that the increased functional value of a product can increase the purchase intention of consumers. We collected the outcomes of the detailed investigation of functional values from the closed-ended questionnaire, and the statistics showed that the mean value of functional values was 3.957, from three questions. Among the three questions, the lowest mean was "I will only buy products that have features I can use, in e-commerce platforms." which is equal to 3.91, which is lower than the average. The highest standard deviation is "I will only buy products that have features I can use, in e-commerce platforms." is 1.166. This means that respondents have very different views on this issue. Therefore, companies should focus on what makes a product valuable to consumers in order to increase their purchase intention, as the results show that most consumers will choose products that are useful to them.

5.3 Recommendations

From the results, the findings of this study suggest that there is an association between the variables that ultimately affect purchase intention. A portion of the relationship between the variables also affects purchase intention. The correlates in the study, personality traits affect emotional trust, while emotional trust, personality traits, cognitive engagement and functional value are significant on purchase intention.

Firstly, for the aspect of personality traits, companies should be more involved in consumer research. For example, demand for a product is greater in groups of boys or girls, introverts or extroverts. This is because it is clear from the findings that personality traits influence the emotional trust of consumers. So, for example, for customers with extroverted personalities, regular phone calls to collect after-use feelings of products and chat with customers appropriately. Then for introverted customers, regular messages should be sent to customers, and questionnaires should be used to collect their feelings after using the products.

The second aspect of personality traits is that they influence purchase intentions. This is because the relationship between personality traits and purchase intention is significant from the findings. Therefore,

companies need to regularly research consumer preferences and personality traits. For example, extroverted people will often recommend products to their friends, so for extroverted customers, companies can make several phone calls and sales pitches. For introverts, companies can use SMS to communicate. For the emotional trust aspect, companies need to increase consumer trust in order to gain more purchase intent. For example, the safety of the company's products and the positive impact the company plays in society is constantly promoted through the media, including but not limited to visits to elderly homes and orphanages. This allows consumers to see that the company is actively giving back to society and increases their trust in the company. For the cognitive engagement aspect, using the results of the study can help companies realize that engaging consumers in interaction with their products can be beneficial in increasing company sales. For example, in shopping malls or shops, set up display spaces, hire professional company employees to introduce the products, invite customers to experience them live and answer their questions. Only by increasing consumer involvement can consumers be motivated to buy. For the functional value aspect, based on the results of the research, the company can create products based on products that have utility, or more precisely, consumer value needs. For example, making the packaging of the product into bags that can be used twice, small storage containers, etc. As this increases the functional value of the product and makes it more valuable to the consumer in terms of functionality, this will increase the consumer's purchase intention and make them more likely to choose the product.

Overall, the results of this study can help companies to better understand that there are four factors that can really influence consumers' purchase intentions. These factors are personality traits, emotional trust, perceived engagement and functional value. A positive increase in any one of these factors will increase consumer purchase intent. This is a very important finding for companies that are looking to increase sales in the future to make more profit.

5.4 Further Study

Due to time constraints and the prevalence of the COVID-19, this study focused on only four variables that influence Chinese online consumers' purchase intention factors, namely personality traits, affective trust, cognitive involvement, and functional value, with mid-term personality traits also influencing consumer affective trust. For further research, it is necessary to conduct a similar study to identify other relevant factors

that have an impact on purchase intention. Similar studies should be added in order to obtain more comprehensive information and understanding of the factors influencing purchase intention. In addition, further research should be conducted on a larger sample and population size to increase the generalizability and credibility of the study. In addition, another research might be done to examine the connection between demographic characteristics and purchase intentions in other countries. This may present more and better studies and may yield different results.

REFERENCES

- Allport, G. W. (1937). *Personality: A psychological interpretation*.
- Ansoff, H. I., Kipley, D., Lewis, A. O., Helm-Stevens, R., & Ansoff, R. (2018). *Implanting strategic management*. Springer.
- Ajzen, I. (2005). *Attitudes, personality and behaviour*. McGraw-hill education (UK).
- Bosnjak, M., Galesic, M., & Tuten, T. (2007). Personality determinants of online shopping: Explaining online purchase intentions using a hierarchical approach. *Journal of Business Research*, 60(6), 597-605.
- Brakus, J. J., Schmitt, B. H., & Zarantonello, L. (2009). Brand experience: what is it? How is it measured? Does it affect loyalty? *Journal of marketing*, 73(3), 52-68.
- Babin, B. J., Darden, W. R., & Griffin, M. (1994). Work and/or fun: measuring hedonic and utilitarian shopping value. *Journal of consumer research*, 20(4), 644-656.
- Cassell, J., & Bickmore, T. (2000). External manifestations of trustworthiness in the interface. *Communications of the ACM*, 43(12), 50-56.
- Cochran, L. (1997). *Career counseling: A narrative approach*. Sage publications.
- Cho, C. H. (1999). How advertising works on the WWW: Modified elaboration likelihood model. *Journal of Current Issues & Research in Advertising*, 21(1), 34-50.
- Chang, P. L., & Chieng, M. H. (2006). Building consumer-brand relationship: A cross-cultural experiential view. *Psychology & Marketing*, 23(11), 927-959.
- Carlyle, T. (1841). *German Romance: Specimens of Its Chief Authors (Vol. 1)*. J. Munroe.
- Cattell, R. B. (1973). *Personality and mood by questionnaire*. Jossey-Bass.
- Cahyorini, A., & Rusfian, E. Z. (2012). The effect of packaging design on impulsive buying. *BISNIS & BIROKRASI: Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi dan Organisasi*, 18(1)
- Chang, H. H., & Wang, H. W. (2011). The moderating effect of customer perceived value on online shopping behaviour. *Online information review*.
- deMorais Watanabe, E. A., Alfinito, S., Curvelo, I. C. G., & Hamza, K. M. (2020). Perceived value, trust and purchase intention of organic food: a study with Brazilian consumers. *British Food Journal*, 122(4), 1070-1184.
- Dunning, D., Fetchenhauer, D., & Schlösser, T. M. (2012). Trust as a social and emotional act: Noneconomic considerations in trust behavior. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 33(3), 686-694.
- Demoulin, N., & Willems, K. (2019). Servicescape irritants and customer satisfaction: The moderating role of shopping motives and involvement. *Journal of Business Research*, 104, 295-306.
- Dodds, W. B., Monroe, K. B., & Grewal, D. (1991). Effects of price, brand, and store information on buyers' product evaluations. *Journal of marketing research*, 28(3), 307-319.
- Deng, P. (2009). Why do Chinese firms tend to acquire strategic assets in international expansion? *Journal of world business*, 44(1), 74-84.
- Engström, A., Styvén, M. E., Wallström, Å., & Salehi-Sangari, E. (2015). Developing an attractive mobile service: A comparison of desired consumption values of three different services. *In the Sustainable Global Marketplace* (pp. 454-456). Springer, Cham.
- Eroglu, S. A., Machleit, K. A., & Davis, L. M. (2003). Empirical testing of a model of online store atmospherics and shopper responses. *Psychology & marketing*, 20(2), 139-150.
- Eysenck, H. J. (1967). *The biological basis of personality (Vol. 689)*. Transaction publishers.
- Friedman, J., Hastie, T., & Tibshirani, R. (2000). Additive logistic regression: a statistical view of boosting (with discussion and a rejoinder by the authors). *The annals of statistics*, 28(2), 337-407.

24. Ghosh, A. (1990). Frequency-dependent conductivity in bismuth-vanadate glassy semiconductors. *Physical review B*, 41(3), 1479.
25. Hancock, P. A., Billings, D. R., Schaefer, K. E., Chen, J. Y., De Visser, E. J., & Parasuraman, R. (2011). A meta-analysis of factors affecting trust in human-robot interaction. *Human factors*, 53(5), 517-527.
26. Hong, I. B. (2015). Understanding the consumer's online merchant selection process: The roles of product involvement, perceived risk, and trust expectation. *International Journal of Information Management*, 35(3), 322-336.
27. Hirschman, E. C., & Holbrook, M. B. (1982). Hedonic consumption: emerging concepts, methods and propositions. *Journal of marketing*, 46(3), 92-101.
28. Harrison, D. A., Price, K. H., Gavin, J. H., & Florey, A. T. (2002). Time, teams, and task performance: Changing effects of surface-and deep-level diversity on group functioning. *Academy of management journal*, 45(5), 1029-1045.
29. Hemmerling, S., Hamm, U., & Spiller, A. (2015). Consumption behaviour regarding organic food from a marketing perspective—a literature review. *Organic Agriculture*, 5(4), 277-313.
30. Huang, E. (2012). Online experiences and virtual goods purchase intention. *Internet Research*.
31. Jiang, Z., Chan, J.C., Tan, B.C., & Chua, W.S. (2010). Effects of Interactivity on Website Involvement and Purchase Intention. *J. Assoc. Inf. Syst.*, 11, 1
32. Khare, A., Khare, A., & Singh, S. (2010). Role of consumer personality in determining preference for online banking in India. *Journal of Database Marketing & Customer Strategy Management*, 17(3), 174-187.
33. Kraus, S., Clauss, T., Breier, M., Gast, J., Zardini, A., & Tiberius, V. (2020). The economics of COVID-19: initial empirical evidence on how family firms in five European countries cope with the corona crisis. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*.
34. Kao, H. M. (2017). Exploring Personality Trait and Purchase Intention-the Mediator of Legal and Ethical Responsibilities of Third-Party Payment. *The Journal of International Management Studies*, 12(2), 48-57.
35. Kawa, L. W., Rahmadiani, S. F., & Kumar, S. (2013). Factors affecting consumer decision-making: a survey of young-adults on imported cosmetics in Jabodetabek, Indonesia. *SIJ Transactions on Industrial, Financial & Business Management*, 1(5), 175-180.
36. Khraim, H. S. (2011). The influence of brand loyalty on cosmetics buying behavior of UAE female consumers. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 3(2), 123.
37. Koshazadeh, S. A., Rahimniya, F., & Afkhami Rohani, H. (2012). The Effect of Trust in Management on Organizational Strategic Thinking and Their Role in Organizational Performance Improvement through Organizational Commitment in Higher Education. *Journal of New Approaches in Educational Administration*, 3(12), 163-187.
38. Kirkpatrick, S. A., & Locke, E. A. (1996). Direct and indirect effects of three core charismatic leadership components on performance and attitudes. *Journal of applied psychology*, 81(1), 36.
39. Keller, K. L. (2001). Building customer-based brand equity: A blueprint for creating strong brands.
40. Kollock, P. (1999). The production of trust in online markets. *Advances in group processes*, 16(1), 99-123.
41. Koufaris, M. (2002). Applying the technology acceptance model and flow theory to online consumer behavior. *Information systems research*, 13(2), 205-223.
42. Lee, C. H., Eze, U. C., & Ndubisi, N. O. (2011). Analyzing key determinants of online repurchase intentions. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*.
43. Long, M. M., & Schiffman, L. G. (2000). Consumption values and relationships: segmenting the market for frequency programs. *Journal of consumer marketing*.
44. Lewis, S. L., Lloyd, J., Sitch, S., Mitchard, E. T., & Laurance, W. F. (2009). Changing ecology of tropical forests: evidence and drivers. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, 40, 529-549.
45. Lerner, J. S., & Keltner, D. (2000). Beyond valence: Toward a model of emotion-specific influences on judgement and choice. *Cognition & emotion*, 14(4), 473-493.
46. Liu, Y., & Shrum, L. J. (2002). What is interactivity and is it always such a good thing? Implications of

- definition, person, and situation for the influence of interactivity on advertising effectiveness. *Journal of advertising*, 31(4), 53-64.
47. McKnight, D. H., Choudhury, V., & Kacmar, C. (2002). Developing and validating trust measures for e-commerce: An integrative typology. *Information systems research*, 13(3), 334-359.
 48. Matthews, G., Deary, I. J., & Whiteman, M. C. (2003). *Personality traits*. Cambridge University Press.
 49. Mathwick, C., Malhotra, N., & Rigdon, E. (2001). Experiential value: conceptualization, measurement and application in the catalog and Internet shopping environment. *Journal of retailing*, 77(1), 39-56.
 50. McMillan, S. J., Hwang, J. S., & Lee, G. (2003). Effects of structural and perceptual factors on attitudes toward the website. *Journal of advertising research*, 43(4), 400-409.
 51. McKnight, D. H., & Chervany, N. L. (2001). What trust means in e-commerce customer relationships: An interdisciplinary conceptual typology. *International journal of electronic commerce*, 6(2), 35-59.
 52. Nuttavuthisit, K., & Thøgersen, J. (2017). The importance of consumer trust for the emergence of a market for green products: The case of organic food. *Journal of business ethics*, 140(2), 323-337.
 53. O'Cass, A. (2000). An assessment of consumers product, purchase decision, advertising and consumption involvement in fashion clothing. *Journal of economic psychology*, 21(5), 545-576.
 54. Park, C. W., & Young, S. M. (1986). Consumer response to television commercials: The impact of involvement and background music on brand attitude formation. *Journal of marketing research*, 23(1), 11-24.
 55. Peter, J. P. (1979). Reliability: A review of psychometric basics and recent marketing practices. *Journal of marketing research*, 16(1), 6-17.
 56. Palmer, B., Jones, R. J., Wina, E., & Tangendjaja, B. (2000). The effect of sample drying conditions on estimates of condensed tannin and fibre content, dry matter digestibility, nitrogen digestibility and PEG binding of *Calliandra calothyrsus*. *Animal Feed Science and Technology*, 87(1-2), 29-40.
 57. Papadopoulou, P., Andreou, A., Kanellis, P., & Martakos, D. (2001). Trust and relationship building in electronic commerce. *Internet research*, 11(4), 322-332.
 58. Pavlou, P. A. (2003). Consumer acceptance of electronic commerce: Integrating trust and risk with the technology acceptance model. *International journal of electronic commerce*, 7(3), 101-134.
 59. Punj, G., & Stewart, D. W. (1983). Cluster analysis in marketing research: Review and suggestions for application. *Journal of marketing research*, 20(2), 134-148.
 60. Koshazadeh, S. A., Rahimniya, F., & Afkhami Rohani, H. (2012). The Effect of Trust in Management on Organizational Strategic Thinking and Their Role in Organizational Performance Improvement through Organizational Commitment in Higher Education. *Journal of New Approaches in Educational Administration*, 3(12), 163-187.
 61. Ramayah, T., Ling, N. S., Taghizadeh, S. K., & Rahman, S. A. (2016). Factors influencing SMEs website continuance intention in Malaysia. *Telematics and Informatics*, 33(1), 150-164.
 62. Resnick, P., Kuwabara, K., Zeckhauser, R., & Friedman, E. (2000). Reputation systems. *Communications of the ACM*, 43(12), 45-48.
 63. Sirohi, N., McLaughlin, E. W., & Wittink, D. R. (1998). A model of consumer perceptions and store loyalty intentions for a supermarket retailer. *Journal of retailing*, 74(2), 223-245.
 64. Sweeney, J. C., & Soutar, G. N. (2001). Consumer perceived value: The development of a multiple item scale. *Journal of retailing*, 77(2), 203-220.
 65. Smith, S. E., & Read, D. J. (2010). *Mycorrhizal symbiosis*. Academic press.
 66. Smillie, L. D., Cooper, A. J., Wilt, J., & Revelle, W. (2012). Do extraverts get more bang for the buck? Refining the affective-reactivity hypothesis of extraversion. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 103(2), 306.
 67. Smillie, L. D. (2013). Extraversion and reward processing. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 22(3), 167-172.
 68. Shah, A. K., Mullainathan, S., & Shafir, E. (2012). Some consequences of having too little. *Science*, 338(6107), 682-685.
 69. Shafir, E., Simonson, I., & Tversky, A. (1993). Reason-based choice. *Cognition*, 49(1-2), 11-36.
 70. Schembri, S. (2009). Reframing brand experience: The experiential meaning of Harley-

- Davidson. *Journal of Business Research*, 62(12), 1299-1310.
71. Tan, Y. H., & Thoen, W. (2000). An outline of a trust model for electronic commerce. *Applied Artificial Intelligence*, 14(8), 849-862.
72. Tian, J., Chen, Y., & Wang, L. (2014). Research on the Relationship between Online Reviews and Customer Purchase Intention: The Moderating Role of Personality Trait. WHICEB.
73. Teng, C. C., & Wang, Y. M. (2015). Decisional factors driving organic food consumption: Generation of consumer purchase intentions. *British Food Journal*.
74. Van Den Berg, R. J., & Van Lieshout, J. M. (2001). Finding symbols for cyberspace: addressing the issues of trust in electronic commerce. *Production Planning & Control*, 12(5), 514-524.
75. Watanabe, H., Domei, T., Morimoto, T., Natsuaki, M., Shiomi, H., Toyota, T., & STOPDAPT-2 Investigators. (2019). Effect of 1-month dual antiplatelet therapy followed by clopidogrel vs 12-month dual antiplatelet therapy on cardiovascular and bleeding events in patients receiving PCI: the STOPDAPT-2 randomized clinical trial. *Jama*, 321(24), 2414-2427.
76. Xiao, L., Guo, F., Yu, F., & Liu, S. (2019). The effects of online shopping context cues on consumers' purchase intention for cross-border E-Commerce sustainability. *Sustainability*, 11(10), 2777.
77. Zaichkowsky, J. L. (1986). Conceptualizing involvement. *Journal of advertising*, 15(2), 4-34.
78. Zarantonello, L., Jedidi, K., & Schmitt, B. H. (2013). Functional and experiential routes to persuasion: An analysis of advertising in emerging versus developed markets. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 30(1), 46-56.
79. Zeithaml, V. A., Berry, L. L., & Parasuraman, A. (1996). The behavioral consequences of service quality. *Journal of marketing*, 60(2), 31-46.
80. Zhu, W., Mou, J., & Benyoucef, M. (2019). Exploring purchase intention in cross-border E-commerce: A three stage model. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 51, 320-330.